

PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS AND THEIR
ORGANIZATION

Isomova Farog'at Tojiddin qizi

Asian International University

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology

E-mail: isomovafarogattojiddinqizi@oxu.uz

Annotation : Preschool education organizations are in the article types and the process of their organization, the professional and personal competencies of the leader in this process are highlighted.

Key words : non-state, competence, knowledge, skills, competence, development, communication, education, training, inclusive education.

DOSHKOLNYE OBRAZOVATELNYE ORGANIZATION I IX ORGANIZATION

Annotation: V state opisany vidy doshkolnyx obrazovatelnyx organizatsiy i process ix organizatsii, a takje professionalnye i lichnostnye kompetentsii rukovatelya v etom protesse.

Key words: negosudarstvennoe, kompetentnost, znaniya, umeniya, kompetentnost, razvitie, obshchenie, obrazovanie, vospitanie, inklyuzivnoe obrazovanie.

PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS AND THEIR ORGANIZATION

Abstract: The article describes the types of preschool educational organizations and the process of their organization, as well as the professional and personal competencies of the leader in this process.

Key words: non-state, competence, knowledge, skills, competence, development, communication, education, upbringing, inclusive education.

Today, development strategies are being defined in our developing country. Therefore, the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 ensures the prosperity and continuous progress of our country. Education is the main driving factor of development. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "No matter what field we choose, we cannot achieve any changes or a prosperous life without educating modern mature personnel." The words that prepare such personnel, a healthy gene pool of the nation, first of all, start from the pre-school education system, are a clear proof of our above-mentioned opinion. The effectiveness of the preschool education system in our country depends on the properly organized educational process. In order to further develop the preschool education system, many preschool education organizations are being established in our country. In turn, preschool education organizations are divided into 2 types according to the form of organization.

1) State pre-school educational organizations . Organizations of this type are organized in the following ways based on their goals and tasks.

- general preschool education organization;
- multidisciplinary specialized pre-school education organization;
- preschool education organization with inclusive groups;
- joint preschool educational organization.

Implementation of the state educational program of preschool education and upbringing is ensured in the general development groups of the preschool education organization of general type.

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The implementation of the state educational program of preschool education and upbringing for children with physical or mental disabilities in the multidisciplinary specialized preschool education organization is ensured.

In a pre-school education organization with inclusive groups, equal opportunities for education and upbringing are ensured by integrating children into a healthy environment, taking into account their special educational needs and individual capabilities.

The state regulation of preschool education and upbringing aimed at organizing the education and upbringing of children with physical or mental disabilities and children without developmental disabilities in a single organization in separate groups, as well as in inclusive groups, in a joint preschool education organization. This program will be implemented.

The state preschool education organization is established as a legal entity and performs its activities on the basis of the charter.

2). Non-state pre-school education organizations.

Non-state pre-school education organizations are established as legal entities and carry out their activities on the basis of a charter and a license in the field of pre-school education and upbringing. These organizations are divided into two groups.

- MTT in public private partnership (family MTT)

A maximum of 50 children of preschool age are allowed to receive education and upbringing in family non-governmental preschool educational organizations. Organization of such organizations is carried out in cooperation between a legal entity and the state.

- Non-governmental preschool education organization.

A non-governmental preschool education organization is established by the founder in the form of a legal entity and performs its activities on the basis of a charter and a license in the field of preschool education and upbringing.

Leading methodical work in a preschool educational organization is part of the job qualification of a methodologist. In this process, the methodist gives instructions to all pedagogical staff on the use of various methods and tools in order to increase the effectiveness of education. He finds a way. He takes the initiative to hold a pedagogical council with the director of the Methodist preschool education organization. The Pedagogical Council raises the most urgent topics in the organization of preschool education, makes suggestions on eliminating deficiencies in the educational process, increasing the level of professional knowledge of educators. The Pedagogical Council also offers to popularize Methodist best practices and provides necessary guidelines for educators to popularize their work. It also includes issues related to the education and upbringing of the children on the agenda.

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